

1 **Title: T Cell Receptor Precision Editing of Regulatory T Cells for Celiac Disease**

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41 immunodominant deamidated peptides exert bystander suppression *in vivo*.

42

43 Abstract:

44 Celiac disease (CeD), a gluten-sensitive enteropathy, demonstrates a strong HLA association
45 with >90% of the patients expressing HLA-DQ2.5. No therapy is available for the condition
46 except for a lifelong gluten-free diet. Here, the therapeutic potential of regulatory T cells (Tregs)
47 is explored. By orthotopic replacement of TCRs through homology-directed repair we
48 generated gluten-reactive HLA-DQ2.5-restricted CD4⁺ engineered (e) T effector cells (Teffs)
49 and eTregs and performed *in vivo* experiments in HLA-DQ2.5 transgenic mice. Of five
50 validated TCRs, TCRs specific for two immunodominant and deamidated gluten epitopes
51 (DQ2.5-glia- α 1a and DQ2.5-glia- α 2) were selected for further evaluation. CD4⁺ eTeffs
52 exposed to deamidated gluten through oral gavage interacted with dendritic and B cells in the
53 Peyer's patches and gut-draining lymph nodes, and specifically migrated to the intestine. The
54 suppressive function of human eTregs correlated with high TCR functional activity.
55 Importantly, eTregs specific for one epitope suppressed the proliferation and gut migration of
56 CD4⁺ eTeffs specific for the same and the other gluten epitope, demonstrating bystander
57 suppression. The suppression requires an antigen-specific activation of eTregs as polyclonal
58 Tregs failed to suppress CD4⁺ eTeffs. The findings highlight the therapeutic potential of gluten-
59 reactive eTregs redirected against immunodominant epitopes in CeD.

60

61 Main text:

62 **Introduction**

63 Celiac disease (CeD) is a chronic inflammatory disorder of the small intestine with a global
64 prevalence of about 1% (1). The condition is caused by a maladapted immune response to cereal
65 gluten proteins which causes tissue damage in the gut and the formation of autoantibodies to
66 the enzyme transglutaminase 2 (2). CeD has a strong HLA association to the HLA-DQ2.5,
67 HLA-DQ2.2 and HLA-DQ8 allotypes with most patients carrying HLA-DQ2.5 (3). These
68 HLA-DQ molecules are involved in the pathogenesis by preferentially presenting deamidated
69 gluten epitopes to antigen-reactive CD4⁺ T cells (2, 4). The only available treatment for CeD is
70 a strict and lifelong gluten-free diet. This dietary intervention represents a major socioeconomic
71 burden for patients and is associated with psychological morbidities, social isolation and
72 unbalanced nutrition (5, 6). Additionally, despite strict adherence to a gluten-free diet, up to
73 30% of patients experience persistent symptoms and intestinal inflammation (7, 8). Therefore,
74 there is an unmet need for developing alternative curative approaches including restoration of
75 an immune tolerance to gluten (9).

76

77 Adoptive transfer of regulatory T cells (Tregs) has demonstrated feasibility and safety in diverse
78 clinical trials for the treatment of type 1 diabetes (T1D), Crohn's disease, systemic lupus
79 erythematosus (SLE), pemphigus, graft-versus-host disease (GvHD), and allotransplantation
80 (10-12). Lessons learned from these early clinical trials, but also preclinical models, highlighted
81 the need for antigen-specificity (10). To overcome the low frequency of circulating antigen-
82 specific Tregs, Treg specificity can be redirected by engineering T cell receptors (TCR) or
83 chimeric antigen receptors (CAR). While CARs have the main advantage of being HLA-
84 unrestricted, they are less sensitive than TCRs (10). On the other hand, TCRs are limited by
85 HLA restrictions reducing the number of patients who can potentially be treated with the same

86 therapy. In this setting, CeD is attractive with most patients being HLA-DQ2.5 (encoded by
87 various *DQA1*05* and *DQB1*02* alleles) (3).

88

89 Proline and glutamine-rich gluten proteins of wheat (gliadins and glutenins), barley (hordeins),
90 and rye (secalins) can give rise to deamidated T cell epitopes that bind strongly to HLA-DQ2.5
91 (13). Such T cell epitopes are generated as a result of proline-rich fragments being resistant to
92 intestinal proteolytic degradation and with particular glutamine residues being targeted by
93 transglutaminase 2 (TG2) for conversion to glutamate (2). Deamidated glutamine residues at
94 positions 4, 6, and 7 facilitate the anchoring of the epitopes to HLA-DQ2.5. Thus, compared to
95 other HLA molecules, HLA-DQ2.5 can present a large repertoire of gluten-derived peptides.
96 Several gluten-derived HLA-DQ2.5-restricted T cell epitopes have been identified (13, 14).
97 Some epitopes, including DQ2.5-glia- α 1a and DQ2.5-glia- α 2 derived from α -gliadin proteins
98 and DQ2.5-glia- ω 1 and DQ2.5-glia- ω 2 derived from ω -gliadin proteins, are recognized by
99 CD4⁺ T cells of most CeD patients and considered immunodominant (13).

100

101 We hypothesized that Tregs can be redirected against gluten by introducing specific TCRs into
102 their genome. By orthotopic replacement of TCRs through homology-directed repair, we
103 generated gluten-reactive HLA-DQ2.5-restricted CD4⁺ engineered effector (eTeffs) and
104 regulatory (eTregs) T cells specific for either DQ2.5-glia- α 1a and DQ2.5-glia- α 2 (hereafter
105 glia- α 1a and glia- α 2 for short). Using these T cells, we tested the ability of eTregs to suppress
106 gluten-induced T cell responses *in vitro* and *in vivo*. We observed antigen-dependent bystander
107 suppression in that Tregs specific for one gluten epitope not only suppressed activation of T
108 cells specific for the same gluten epitope but also the activation of T cells specific for a different
109 epitope. Given the plethora of gluten T cell epitopes in CeD, eTregs thus hold a potential to

110 suppress immune response to all pathogenic gluten epitopes and to restore tolerance to gluten

111 in CeD patients.

112

113 **Results**

114 **Five gluten-specific TCRs were successfully re-cloned, validated, and orthotopically**
115 **inserted into the TRAC locus of primary T cells**

116 We selected TCRs of five gluten-reactive T cell clones, two specific for the gliadin- α 1a epitope
117 (S2, LS2.8) and three for the gliadin- α 2 epitope (D2, JR5.1, S16) (15) (Fig. 1A). Deamidated α -
118 gliadin peptides harboring the gliadin- α 1a and gliadin- α 2 epitopes were synthesized to test T cell
119 reactivity either as shorter peptides representing single epitopes, as a 33-mer fragment
120 representing several gliadin- α 1a and gliadin- α 2 epitopes (gliadin- α _33mer) or as a peptide containing
121 one copy of gliadin- α 1a and one copy of gliadin- α 2 (gliadin- α 2-1a) (Fig. 1B). To validate the specificity
122 of the selected TCRs, we used a TCR screening platform consisting of electroporating
123 messenger RNA into a transgenic TCR KO cell line expressing luciferase under the control of
124 a NFAT reporter (Figure 1C, Fig. S1A-B). The transfected cells were co-cultured with an HLA-
125 DQ2.5⁺ β 2-microglobulin (β 2m) KO lymphoblast-like Raji cell line (Fig. S1C) pulsed with
126 peptides representing the gliadin epitopes or a control CLIP2 peptide. Eighteen hours after
127 activation, Jurkat cells expressed CD3 and TCR (Fig. 1D) and showed a peptide-specific NFAT
128 activity (Fig. 1E, Fig. S2).

129

130 We next cloned the five TCRs into an adeno-associated virus (AAV) vector to orthotopically
131 replace the endogenous TCR of primary T cells by homology-directed repair (HDR) as
132 previously described (16). Using GFP as a surrogate, we first confirmed that AAV transduction
133 alone was insufficient to observe transgene expression (Fig. S3), as previously showed by
134 others (17, 18). The variable alpha-chain and the variable and constant beta-chains for each
135 TCR were cloned in a single gene cassette (Fig. 1F). To avoid mispairing, the TCR beta constant
136 gene (*TRBC*) was also deleted. Purified CD4⁺ or CD8⁺ T cells were expanded with a K562 cell
137 line transduced with CD64 and CD86 (Fig. S1D) and anti-CD3 antibodies (OKT3) (Fig. 1G).

138 Editing efficiency reached 95% for TCR KO and over 60% for TCR KI (Fig. 1H-I, Fig. S4A-
139 B). Cells remained viable over time and expanded similarly across all five engineered TCRs
140 (eTCRs) and independent donors (Fig. 1J and Fig. S4C). As human donors were not selected
141 to be HLA-DQ2.5⁺, we used β 2m KO Raji cells, naturally expressing HLA-DQ2.5, to evaluate
142 the TCR specificity/activity. Importantly, CD25 and CD71 upregulation was peptide-dependent
143 (Fig. 1K-L and Fig. S4D-E) and comparable independently of the antigen-presenting cells
144 (APCs) used (β 2m KO Raji cells vs monocyte-derived dendritic cells, vs B cells) (Fig. S5).

145

146 **Functional activity of five gluten-reactive TCRs is modulated by peptide sequence and its** 147 **co-receptor**

148 We next assessed the functional avidity of these eTCRs in a dose-response activation assay
149 based on CD25 and CD71 upregulation. The half maximal effective concentration (EC50)
150 showed overlapping 95% interval confidence for the $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 1a and $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 2 specific TCRs
151 despite that the reported K_m for these TCRs vary (ranging from 16 to 248 μ M) (15) (Fig. 2A).
152 Interestingly, the functional avidity of the TCRs were higher for the deamidated 33mer as
153 compared to the shorter peptides, similar to what has previously been observed for other glia-
154 α 1a and $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 2 specific TCRs (19, 20). Also, when pulsing APCs with an artificial hybrid
155 peptide ($\text{glia-}\alpha$ 2-1a) without the N-terminal QLQ sequence, the functional activity of the glia-
156 α 1- but not $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 2-specific TCRs was 10-100 times reduced suggesting that the presentation
157 of the $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 1 epitope is decreased (Fig 2A). Importantly, CD8⁺ T cells with eTCRs were also
158 specifically activated but with a higher EC50 (Fig 2B, Fig. S6). We selected the TCRs S2 and
159 D2 for subsequent experiments as they exhibited the highest overall responsiveness for their
160 corresponding epitopes and as we observed no competition when CD4⁺ eTeffs were exposed to
161 $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 1a and $\text{glia-}\alpha$ 2 containing peptides at the same time (Fig. S7).

162

163 **Engineered murine CD4⁺ eTeffs proliferate in the gut-draining lymph nodes and infiltrate**
164 **the small intestine lamina propria after oral gavage of gliadin**

165 We next sought to define the proliferation capacities of CD4⁺ eTeffs *in vivo*. We orthotopically
166 replaced the endogenous TCR of murine CD4⁺ T cells using the Ark313 synthetic AAV evolved
167 variant (17). Two AAVs were produced, one with the TRAC and TRBC sgRNA expression
168 cassettes (AAV sgRNA), and a second AAV for delivering the transgenic TCR together with a
169 green fluorescent protein (GFP) reporter gene (AAV eTCR) (Fig. 3A). To avoid
170 electroporation, CD4⁺ T cells from Cas9⁺ C57BL/6 (B6-Cas9) transgenic mice were used for
171 editing (Fig. 3B). Functional assays were performed with matured bone-marrow-derived
172 dendritic cells (BMDCs) expanded from HLA-DQ2.5⁺ C57BL/6 mice (B6-DQ2.5) (Fig. S8).
173 KO and KI efficiencies were over 98 and 40% respectively (Fig. 3C-D). Cells expanded over
174 100-fold after ten days of culture (Fig. 3E) and both TCRs upregulated CD25 and CD69 in a
175 peptide-specific manner (Fig. 3F-G). Similar to what was observed for human T cells, the EC50
176 95% confidence intervals were overlapping for both epitopes (Fig. 3H). These results were
177 confirmed by a CFSE dilution assay (Fig. S9).

178
179 To monitor the trafficking of gluten-reactive CD4⁺ eTeffs *in vivo*, we added a retroviral
180 transduction step to the TCR editing to insert the luciferase (Luc) and Thy1.1 (CD90.1) reporter
181 genes (Fig. 3I). At the end of the culture, almost all cells expressed Thy1.1 and over 30% the
182 S2-TCR (Fig. 3J). Adoptive cell transfer (ACT) of 2x10⁶ Thy1.1⁺CD3⁺CFSE⁺CD4⁺ T cells into
183 B6-DQ2.5 mice was performed (Fig. 3K). We divided mice into three groups: (a) gluten-free
184 diet (since birth), (b) standard gluten-containing chow (since birth), and (c) gluten-free diet
185 (since birth) with an oral gavage of the deamidated 33mer α -gliadin peptide (further referred as
186 gliadin) one day after ACT (Fig. 3L). Only mice who received gliadin gavage showed stronger
187 bioluminescence in the abdominal region on days two and four after ACT (Fig. 3M). These

188 results were confirmed by flow cytometry of T cells suggesting that gliadin deamidation is not
189 taking place in mice fed with standard gluten-containing chow (Fig. S10). Of note, the total
190 abdominal flux of the S2 and D2 CD4⁺ eTeffs was significantly higher than with polyclonally
191 expanded T cells (Fig. S11).

192

193 We next evaluated CD4⁺ eTeff gluten-dependent proliferation in the intestine and
194 interconnected lymph nodes (LNs) of the pancreatic and mesenteric regions (Fig 3N), as
195 previously described (21). Five days after ACT (Fig 3O), cells were retrieved from the lamina
196 propria of the duodenum, jejunum, and ileum and from the draining LNs of the liver, pancreas
197 (celiac LN), duodenum, jejunum, ileum, ascending colon, and colon. As controls, we included
198 the mandibular lymph nodes and the spleen. As Cas9 transgenic mice have a low GFP
199 expression, we were able to distinguish the endogenous T cells (GFP^{neg}), non-edited adoptively
200 transferred CD4⁺ T cells (GFP^{low}), and the S2 CD4⁺ eTeffs (GFP^{high}) (Fig. S12). The CD4⁺
201 eTeffs exhibited proliferation across all segments of the small intestine and gut-draining LNs
202 (Fig. 3P-Q, Fig. S12D). Interestingly, the cell trace violet (CTV) mean fluorescence intensity
203 (MFI) of CD4⁺ eTeffs was significantly lower in the small intestine compared to the gut-
204 draining LNs and the spleen, indicating a greater accumulation of proliferated cells in the
205 intestine (Fig. 3R). These results correlated with enhanced expression of the gut-homing
206 chemokine receptor CCR9 and integrin $\alpha 4\beta 7$ (Fig. 3S, Fig. S12E).

207

208 **Specific trafficking of gluten-specific CD4⁺ eTeffs in the mesenteric lymph nodes and** 209 **infiltration of small intestinal villi**

210 We next conducted histological analyses to better understand the mechanisms driving T cell
211 activation and accumulation in the gut. GFP⁺ S2 CD4⁺ eTeffs were injected into B6-DQ2.5
212 mice exposed to PBS or gliadin. Five days later, intestinal tissues were processed as Swiss rolls

213 and cryo-embedded (Fig. 4A-B). The villus, crypt, and Peyer's patch (P-P) regions were
214 visually identified (Fig. 4B). GFP immunostaining was consistently co-expressed with CD4
215 and CD3 (Fig. 4C). Indeed, GFP was not detected in the mesenteric lymph nodes of mice
216 injected with polyclonal GFP^{low} cells (Fig. S13). Importantly, in PBS-exposed mice, CD4⁺
217 eTeffs were not detected in the small intestine and were less abundant in the M-LN and the P-
218 Ps (Fig. 4D). Among the intestinal compartments of gliadin-exposed mice, CD4⁺ eTeffs were
219 preferentially found in the villi, although intra-epithelial CD4⁺ eTeffs were not detected (Fig.
220 4E). When analyzing the lymphoid tissues, CD4⁺ eTeffs were more abundant in the mesenteric
221 lymph nodes than in P-Ps (Fig 4E), and the cells were located mainly in T cell zones (Fig 4F-
222 G). These results suggest that after ACT, engineered cells traffic independently of gliadin into
223 the different lymphoid compartments, and accumulate in the P-Ps of the gut upon gliadin
224 exposure.

225

226 **Gluten-specific CD4⁺ eTeffs mainly interact with CD11c⁺ cells in the small intestine**

227 Since some GFP⁺ cells were also present in the B cell zone (Fig. 4F), we next compared the
228 interaction number of CD4⁺ eTeffs with CD11c⁺ dendritic cells (DCs) and B220⁺ B cells. We
229 found that gliadin-exposed mice had significantly more GFP⁺ cells in the B cell zone, compared
230 to those receiving PBS (Fig. 4H). Interestingly, in the small intestine, CD4⁺ eTeffs were
231 significantly more in contact with DCs and, conversely, with B cells in the lymphoid tissues
232 (Fig. 4I-J). To further study the contribution of B cells in the proliferation of CD4⁺ eTeffs, we
233 treated mice with either an anti-CD20 antibody (clone MB20-11) or a control isotype antibody
234 two weeks prior to adoptive cell transfer. Anti-CD20 treated mice, had a complete depletion of
235 B220⁺CD19⁺ cells in the peripheral blood and the lymphoid organs (mesenteric LNs and spleen)
236 and partial depletion in the small intestine (Fig. S14). Mice received gliadin oral gavage on day
237 one after ACT. Five days after adoptive transfer, CTV⁺ S2 eTeffs showed a significant

238 reduction of the proliferation index in the mesenteric lymph nodes ($P = 0.047$), but not in the
239 small intestine (Fig. 4K). These results suggest that, when deamidated peptides are
240 administered, B cells contribute more to the amplification of eTeff expansion and less to the
241 initiation of the proliferation when the mice are exposed to already deamidated gluten peptides.

242

243 Finally, we examined the interactions of $CD4^+$ eTeffs with the lymphatic and blood vessels. In
244 the mesenteric lymph nodes, $CD4^+$ eTeffs were predominantly in contact with
245 $VEGFR3^+PECAM^+$ lymphatic vessels (Fig. 4L-M). Conversely, in the small intestine, $CD4^+$
246 eTeffs were mostly in contact with $PECAM^+$ blood vessels, supporting the hypothesis that
247 $CD4^+$ eTeffs are primarily licensed in mesenteric lymph nodes where they upregulate CCR9
248 and integrin $\alpha4\beta7$, which then enable their homing to the small intestine through blood
249 circulation.

250

251 **Human eTregs demonstrate superior suppressive activity compared to polyclonally** 252 **expanded Tregs**

253 We next aimed to generate gluten-reactive eTregs and applied the same editing strategy to
254 freshly isolated human $CD25^+CD127^{low}CD4^+$ T cells (Fig. 1F). To obtain sufficient number of
255 eTregs, cells were restimulated with anti-CD3/28 beads on day seven for another five days (Fig.
256 5A-B). Editing efficiency was 80% for TCR KO and 50% for TCR KI (Fig. 5C-D). eTregs
257 expanded 10-12 times without noticeable differences between the S2 and D2 cells (Fig. 5E). At
258 the end of the culture, engineered Tregs remained Foxp3 and Helios high (Fig. 5F-G). To
259 evaluate eTreg antigen-specific suppressive function, we co-cultured CFSE-labeled S2 or D2
260 eTeff with different ratios of polyclonal Treg or eTregs (Fig. 5H). We used the *glia- α 2-1a*
261 peptide, for which clone D2 had lower EC_{50} than clone S2 to compare the suppressive capacity
262 of eTregs with high versus low functional activity, (Fig. 5I, Fig. 2A). The suppressive function

263 was significantly higher upon antigen-specific eTreg activation. Higher suppression was
264 correlated with higher eTreg functional activity for the glia- α 2-1a peptide. Importantly, one
265 eTreg specificity was sufficient to suppress a polyclonal (S2 and D2) T cell proliferation (Fig
266 5J).

267

268 **Gluten-specific murine eTregs suppress CD4⁺ eTeff proliferation in the mesenteric lymph** 269 **nodes and inhibit their migration into the small intestine**

270 To validate the suppressive function of gluten-reactive eTregs *in vivo*, we applied the same
271 editing strategy as for murine CD4⁺ eTeffs by starting with freshly isolated CD4⁺CD25⁺ cells
272 (Fig. 6A). Murine Tregs were expanded for seven days. Editing efficiency was 85% for TCR
273 KO and 25% for TCR KI (Fig. 6B). Tregs expanded 2-10-fold and retained a stable phenotype
274 (Fig. 6C-D). Mice received gliadin gavage one day after ACT and were sacrificed five days
275 later. We first compared the suppression of polyclonal Tregs and S2 eTregs at a 1:1 Treg:Teff
276 ratio. The S2 eTeff were co-transduced with the Thy1.1-luciferase transgene and labeled with
277 CFSE (Fig. 6E-F). At sacrifice, we evaluated the CFSE dilution among the Thy1.1⁺ cell
278 population (Fig. 6G-I). CFSE dilution analysis demonstrated suppression in the small intestine,
279 mesenteric lymph nodes and the spleen only in the S2 eTreg condition confirming the
280 importance of antigen specificity (Fig 6I).

281

282 **Gluten-specific murine eTregs exert bystander suppression mechanisms**

283 To further explore the potential of Tregs to suppress a polyspecific response, we next evaluated
284 the ability of gluten-reactive eTregs to suppress a mixed population of S2 and D2 CD4⁺ eTeffs
285 at a 1:1 Treg:Teff ratio. We compared injection of S2 eTregs, D2 eTregs, and S2 and D2 eTregs
286 together. To follow the specificity of CD4⁺ eTeffs *in vivo*, each TCR cassette included a specific
287 reporter (S2-GFP, D2-Thy1.1) (Fig. 6J). Using this strategy, we could accurately discriminate

288 the S2 eTeffs (GFP^{high}, CTV⁺) and D2 eTeffs (Thy1.1⁺, CTV⁺) (Fig. 6K). Across all conditions,
289 we observed a consistent reduction in CD4⁺ eTeff frequency in the gut and lymphoid organs
290 (Fig. 6L). CTV dilution was also suppressed in the lymphoid organs, and to a lesser extent in
291 the gut. These results suggest that CD4⁺ eTeffs can escape Treg suppression in the lymphoid
292 organs with secondary trafficking to the gut. Notably, we did not observe significantly more
293 suppression when infusing polyspecific eTregs as compared to single-specific eTregs.

294 To further evaluate the bystander suppression of eTregs when exposed to non-overlapping
295 unrelated epitopes, we engineered a gliat- ω 1-specific TCR (clone W321 (22)) flanked to a
296 cherry reporter (Fig. S15). We confirmed that clone W321 recognized only the deamidated
297 34mer derived from ω -gliadin, and did not cross-react with the 33mer derived from the α -
298 gliadin (Fig. S15D). Using the same *in vivo* experimental design, we evaluated the ability of
299 D2 eTregs to suppress a mixed population of D2 and W321 CD4⁺ eTeffs in mice simultaneously
300 exposed to both gliat- α _33mer and gliat- ω _34mer by oral gavage (Fig. 6M). Notably, we found
301 that D2 eTregs suppressed the migration and proliferation of both D2 and W321specific eTeffs.
302 Importantly, we found a consistent reduction in the number of eTeffs migrating into the small
303 intestine across all conditions (Figure S16).

304

305 **Discussion**

306 In this study we functionally validated five TCRs specific for two deamidated gluten epitopes.
307 After intravenous injection, the engineered cells naturally homed to lymphoid tissues and
308 proliferated only in the presence of a deamidated gluten peptide harboring the epitopes.
309 Interestingly, some cells were licensed to traffic into the P-Ps and small intestinal villi and
310 upregulated the gut-homing receptors integrin α 4 β 7 and CCR9. Stimulation of redirected Tregs
311 to a single immunodominant gluten epitope was sufficient to reduce this trafficking and to
312 suppress the proliferation of effector cells in the lymphoid organs. Thus, we demonstrate for

313 the first time that these TCR-engineered regulatory T cells hold therapeutic potential for
314 restoring gluten tolerance in celiac patients.

315

316 Importantly, we demonstrate that eTregs specific for one gluten epitope can suppress activation
317 not only of CD4⁺ eTeffs specific for the same gluten epitope but also of CD4⁺ eTeffs specific
318 for another gluten epitope. Previous studies have shown that the target of mouse and human
319 Treg suppression is not confined to the same antigen, representing a key mechanism of Treg-
320 mediated suppression (23, 24). Interestingly the antigen concentration required to exert
321 suppression may be lower than for T cell activation (23). In CeD, this Treg capacity is critical
322 as it is likely required for the treatment to be effective given the existence of a plethora of gluten
323 T cell epitopes, many yet unidentified (13). In the future, it will be important to demonstrate
324 suppression activity of eTregs against a larger number of other CeD-relevant T cell epitopes
325 including rye of barley epitopes.

326

327 Treg contribution to the natural history of CeD is still controversial. On the one hand, as only a
328 minority of the HLA-DQ2-carrying population develops CeD (2), gluten tolerance failure only
329 rarely occurs. On the other hand, the number of gluten-specific Tregs in the lamina propria of
330 healthy individuals, defined by tetramer-based techniques (25), remains very scarce suggesting
331 that these cells are (1) peripherally-induced and (2) possibly insufficient in numbers when
332 tolerance is broken. Other observations suggest that most gluten-reactive Tregs express CD39
333 and are functionally defective, possibly due to the presence of IL-15 in the gut, a cytokine
334 known to make conventional lymphocytes resistant to Treg suppression (26-28). Additionally,
335 there is an increased number of FOXP3⁺ Tregs in small bowel biopsies of CeD patients with
336 active disease (29, 30). Similar observations were also made in the early phase of organ or tissue
337 rejection (31), fueling the hypothesis that those Tregs are either dysfunctional and/or

338 outnumbered by gluten-specific effector T cells (31, 32). However, the suppressive function of
339 naive circulating polyclonal Tregs in celiac patients appears to be preserved (27). While our
340 study does not provide new insights on the origin of gluten-reactive Tregs, it shows that by
341 redirecting TCR specificity we can shift the balance towards tolerance. These data corroborated
342 previous studies demonstrating that TCR reactivity/specificity in local tissues correlated with
343 Tregs abilities to control inflammation (33).

344

345 Our study found many B-CD4⁺ eTeff interactions, which were gliadin-dependent, in the P-P
346 and, to a lesser extent, in the mesenteric lymph nodes. These data suggest that deamidated
347 peptides are rapidly drained into lymphatics and loaded onto B cells. Thus, the P-P conduit
348 system efficiently transports soluble luminal molecules to the adaptive immune response (34).
349 Strikingly, we also found peptide-specific proliferation in more distant lymphoid organs and
350 the spleen, possibly because deamidated gluten peptides can diffuse in systemic circulation.
351 These results suggest that B cells can be pulsed *in vivo* with deamidated-gluten long peptides.
352 This presentation could contribute to perpetuating the activation and proliferation of gluten-
353 reactive T cells, but also of CeD (TG-2, deamidated or endomysium) specific plasmablasts
354 when co-exposed to gluten-TG2 complexes or celiac-specific haptens (35-37). Therefore,
355 blocking the crosstalk between T and B cells with eTregs may be a key checkpoint for restoring
356 tolerance to gluten.

357

358 Peptide design could substantially influence the functional avidities of the engineered TCRs.
359 The T cell epitopes $\text{glia-}\alpha\text{1a}$ and $\text{glia-}\alpha\text{2}$ share an overlapping seven amino acid core sequence,
360 thus differ by two extra residues at the N- and C-termini, respectively (13). The $\text{glia-}\alpha\text{2-1a}$
361 peptide only induced a moderate activation of the $\text{glia-}\alpha\text{1}$ -specific TCRs likely because the
362 nine-mer core region of this epitope is positioned in the very N-terminus of this peptide. Our

363 study found that high functional activity was necessary for optimal suppression *in vitro*, as also
364 previously reported for GAD and HIP2-5-specific TCRs in type 1 diabetes (38-40). Future
365 studies should still evaluate whether there is a threshold for TCR affinity beyond which the
366 suppressive function of Tregs decrease, as previously reported for effector T cells (41).

367

368 Finally, we noted that all of our gluten-specific TCRs showed specific functional activity if
369 exposed to high peptide concentration. While one study reported the presence of HLA-A2-
370 restricted gluten-specific CD8⁺ T cells in jejunal biopsies of celiac patients (42), HLA-DQ2.5
371 tetramer-positive cells from gut biopsies of untreated CeD patients were only CD4⁺CD8⁻ T cells
372 (43). CD8⁺ intraepithelial lymphocytes (IELs) are activated in a non-TCR dependent manner
373 through NKG2D-MICA interactions in the context of high IL-15 concentrations (2, 44, 45).
374 TCR single-cell sequencing of intraepithelial CD8⁺ T cells revealed a highly diverse and
375 polyclonal repertoire, indicating that new infiltrating IELs in active CeD do not derive from
376 specific single clones but rather from a polyclonal non-specific repertoire. Yet, it would still be
377 interesting to study the reactivity of infiltrating CD8⁺ T cells from CeD patients when
378 challenged with class-I artificially-deficient antigen-presenting cells or B-cells pulsed with
379 gliadin-derived peptides.

380

381 The present study has several limitations. The main one is the absence of intestinal damage
382 upon gluten challenge in our mouse model. Thus, the mice used do not spontaneously mount
383 an immune response against gliadin present in the food. Future studies should aim to induce
384 intestinal damage by either overexpressing IL-15 in the gut (28), or immunizing mice against
385 gluten. Another limitation is related to the short duration of the experiments (five days). We
386 have not evaluated the survival of Tregs over time nor their stability by performing repetitive
387 gluten challenges, as this could lead to Foxp3 loss (46). In addition, the timing of Tregs injection

388 was not evaluated. In the NOD mouse model Tregs effect on Teffs proliferation was more
389 pronounced if injected before (47). Thus, Tregs therapies could also be evaluated in high-risk
390 predisposed patients before disease onset. Finally, no clinical studies evaluated the safety of
391 engineered Tregs using AAVs and multiple double-stranded DNA breaks, limiting the
392 feasibility of our approach for clinical purposes.

393

394 In conclusion, we have demonstrated that adoptively transferred gluten-reactive eTregs can
395 significantly down-modulate the CD4⁺ effector response to gluten epitopes in a B6-DQ2.5
396 mouse model relevant to CeD. Importantly, our study paves the way for a better understanding
397 of key antigen-activating steps following dietary antigen uptake. While further work is needed
398 to assess Treg efficacy in the setting of an active disease, our study provides proof-of-concept
399 evidence that engineered Tregs hold therapeutic potential for restoring gluten tolerance in celiac
400 patients.

401

402 **Materials and methods**

403 **Study design**

404 We hypothesized that gluten-reactive HLA-DQ2.5-restricted Tregs could be engineered and
405 used as a therapeutical strategy to down-modulate pathogenic gluten-reactive CD4⁺ T cells in
406 CeD. The editing strategy relied on CRISPR-Cas9-mediated KO and AAV6-mediated HDR
407 template delivery for human and murine primary T cells. The effect of eTregs was ultimately
408 tested in HLA-DQ2.5⁺ transgenic mice. Investigators were not blinded to the treatment. Details
409 on the number of biological replicates, as well as number of independent experiments are
410 indicated in the figure legends.

411

412 **Human blood products**

413 Deidentified human peripheral blood from healthy donors was ordered at the Swiss Transfusion
414 Center as buffy coats. Donors were not pre-selected to be HLA-DQ2.5⁺. Ficoll-Paque (Cytiva,
415 Uppsala, Sweden, Cat. #17144003) density gradient centrifugation was used to isolate
416 peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs).

417

418 **Animals**

419 HLA-DQ2.5⁺ C57BL/6 (48), and C57BL/6N-Gt(ROSA)26Sor^{em1(CAG-cas9*, -EGFP)Rsky/J} (49)
420 (Jackson, strain #028551) were bred and maintained at the animal facility of the University of
421 Lausanne. Female and male mice were used between 6- and 14-week-old. For experiments
422 assessing the impact of diet on T cell proliferation, mice were kept under a gluten-free diet
423 (Research Diets, New Brunswick, NJ, diet #D11112201) since birth. For all other experiments,
424 both B6-DQ2.5 and B6-Cas9 mice were fed with a standard chow. All mouse experiments were
425 approved by the Cantonal Commission for Animal Experiments from the Canton of Vaud
426 (VD3851, Switzerland).

427

428 **T cell isolation, cell sorting, and flow cytometry**

429 Human CD4⁺ T cells and CD8⁺ T cells were enriched using the EasySep Human CD4⁺ T Cell-
430 and EasySep Human CD8⁺ Isolation Kit, and T cells with Human T Cell Enrichment Kit as per
431 protocols (StemCell Technologies, Vancouver, Canada, Cat. #17952). For human Tregs, CD25⁺
432 cells were enriched from PBMCs with the CD25 MicroBeads II system (Miltenyi Biotec,
433 Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany, Cat. #130-092-983) and further purified based on CD4-FITC,
434 CD25-APC (clone CD25-4E3), and CD127-PE^{low} expression on a BD FACS Aria II cell sorter
435 (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA).

436 Murine CD4⁺ T cells were isolated from pooled LNs and spleens using the EasySep CD4⁺ T
437 Cell Isolation Kit (StemCell Technologies, Vancouver, Canada, Cat. #19852A), following the
438 manufacturer's instructions. For murine Tregs, CD4⁺ T cells were stained with anti-CD4-APC
439 and anti-CD25-PE antibodies. CD4⁺CD25⁺ Tregs and CD4⁺CD25⁻ Teffs were sorted either on
440 a BD FACS Aria II (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA), or on a MoFlo Astrios cell
441 sorter (Beckmann Coulter, Brea, CA, USA).

442 Table S1 provides a list of all antibodies used in this study.

443

444 **In vitro transcription, mRNA transfection, and TCR functional validation**

445 Alpha- and beta-chains of each TCR were cloned with 5' T7 promoter, UTR, and Kozak
446 sequences. In vitro transcription was performed with the HiScribe T7 ARCA mRNA kit (New
447 England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA, Cat. #E2060S), and purified with the Monarch RNA
448 Cleanup kit (New England Biolabs, MA, USA, Cat. #T2030L). Each corresponding alpha- and
449 beta- TCR chains were together electroporated into a Jurkat TCR KO cell line expressing the
450 luciferase gene under the NFAT promoter with the Lonza 4D 96-well electroporation system
451 using pulse code CL-120. Then, 0.1x10⁶ electroporated Jurkat cells per condition were co-

452 cultured overnight with 0.05×10^6 $\beta 2m$ KO Raji cells (1:2 Raji:Jurkat cell ratio) and pulsed with
453 the corresponding peptide at 1 μ M final concentration. Purified anti-CD3 antibody (clone
454 OKT3, BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA, cat. #566685) at 1 μ g/mL was used for
455 positive control, by previously coating the plate wells for 2 hours at 37°C. Three technical
456 replicates were performed. The day after, expression of each TCR was confirmed by flow
457 cytometry.

458

459 **Virus production**

460 AAV6 were produced as previously described (16, 17, 50). Briefly, 25 μ g of pAAV2-ITR
461 containing the cargo vector were mixed with 30 μ g of pDGM6 (containing REP-CAP genes),
462 40 μ g of pAdenovirus (containing VA, E2A, E4 regions (51)) helper plasmids, and 15 nmol of
463 linear polyethylenimine (PEI, Polysciences, Warrington, PA, USA, cat. #23966). For murine
464 cell-infecting AAVs, pDGM6 plasmid was substituted by the Ark313 helper plasmid (17).
465 HEK293T cells were transfected and harvested three days later in AAV lysis buffer (50 mM
466 Tris + 150 mM NaCl). Cells were then lysed by three freeze/thaw cycles, followed by 1h
467 incubation at 37°C with 25 units/mL Benzonase (Millipore Sigma, Burlington, MA, USA, cat.
468 #70-664-3). AAV6 vectors were purified by iodixanol (StemCell Technologies, Vancouver,
469 Canada, cat. #07820) gradient ultracentrifugation. AAVs were thereafter concentrated with 10
470 kDa Amicon columns (Sigma-Aldrich, Cork, Ireland, cat. #UFC901024).

471 Lentiviruses were produced in HEK293T cells using the pCDH-EF1-FHC lentiviral vector
472 (Addgene #64874) (52), pCMV-dR8.9 packaging vector, and the VSV envelope vector
473 pMD2.G, as previously described (16, 53).

474 The murine stem cell virus-based splice-gag vector (pMSGV) retroviral vector was used as
475 backbone to introduce the Thy1.1 and luciferase genes. Retroviruses (RVs) were produced as
476 previously described (54). Briefly, ecotropic platinum-E (Plat-E) retroviral packaging cell line

477 (Cell Biolabs, San Diego, CA, USA, cat. #RV-101) was transduced with 14.3 µg of pCL-Eco
478 helper plasmid and 21.4 µg of the pMSGV plasmid containing the transgenic of interest using
479 5% Turbofect (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #R0532) in Opti-MEM I
480 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #11058021). 48 hours after transfection,
481 cell supernatant was harvested, filtered through a 0.45 µm filter, and concentrated by
482 ultracentrifugation.

483

484 **Human primary T cell editing**

485 High-fidelity Cas9 protein was cloned on the pMJ915 backbone (55) by inserting the R691A
486 point mutation (56), and was recombinantly produced by the Protein Production and Structure
487 Core Facility from the Swiss Institute of Technology in Lausanne (EPFL). CRISPR-Cas9
488 guides were reconstituted as previously described (57, 58). Briefly, two-component guide
489 RNAs (gRNAs) were produced by complexing a crRNA with a tracrRNA (Integrated DNA
490 Technologies (IDT), San Diego, CA, USA). Lyophilized RNAs were resuspended in IDT
491 nuclease-free duplex buffer at a 160 µM final concentration and stored at -80°C. Guides were
492 reconstituted by mixing crRNA and tracrRNA at 1:1 ratio and annealing them at 37°C for 30
493 minutes. Then, 45 µM recombinant high-fidelity Cas9 was added to the 80 µM RNA at a 1:1
494 ratio and incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes. RNPs were kept at 4°C up to two weeks. Guide
495 sequences are listed in Table S3. Human primary cells were electroporated with TRAC and
496 TRBC RNPs on day 2 after activation using the Lonza 4D 96-well electroporation system. Pulse
497 code was EH-115 for Teff, and EO-115 for Treg. After electroporation, cells were resuscitated
498 with pre-warmed serum-free complete medium and rested for 10 minutes at 37°C. Then, cells
499 were collected and AAV was added to the culture for 18-22 hours. Nedisertib (M3814,
500 Selleckchem, Houston, TX, USA, cat. #S8586) was used with Teff only at a concentration of 5
501 µM.

502

503 **Murine primary T cell editing**

504 Cas9-expressing murine primary cells were collected one day after activation, washed,
505 resuspended in serum-free complete medium, and subsequently transduced with both the AAV
506 containing TRAC and TRBC sgRNAs, and the one containing the HDR template for 18-22
507 hours. Cells were then washed and kept in culture.

508 For RV transduction, wells of untreated culture plate were coated overnight at 4°C with 20
509 µg/mL Retronectin (Takara Bio, Kusatsu, Japan, cat. #T100A), following the manufacturer's
510 instructions. On day of T cell transduction, retronectin-precoated wells were washed with PBS,
511 blocked for 30 minutes at 37°C with complete medium. RVs were thereafter added and
512 centrifuged at 2000 G for 1.5 hours at 32 °C. Activated cells were transferred to each coated
513 well, spun at 300 G for 10 minutes. Finally, AAVs were added to the corresponding wells, and
514 cells were incubated at 37°C for 18-22 hours.

515

516 **In vitro suppression assays**

517 Effector T cells were first stained with 1µM CFSE in PBS at room temperature for 5 minutes,
518 washed two times, and resuspended in complete medium without cytokines. Tregs were washed
519 two times and plated in 1:2 serial dilutions up to 1:64. Then, 0.1×10^6 CFSE⁺ eTeffs were added
520 in each condition together with 0.05×10^6 irradiated β2m KO Raji cells and the corresponding
521 peptide at 5 µM. For each experiment, the positive control was co-culture of Teff with APC
522 and peptide only. Co-cultures were incubated for 4 days and CFSE dilution was analyzed by
523 flow cytometry. The proliferation tool in FlowJo software was used to calculate Teff division
524 index (DI, average number of divisions for all cells) for each condition. Percentage of
525 suppression for condition x was calculated with the following formula:

526
$$\left(1 - \frac{DI_{condition\ x}}{DI_{positive\ control}}\right) \times 100$$

527

528 **Murine intestinal leukocyte isolation and lymphoid organ preparation for flow cytometry**

529 Cells from the small intestine lamina propria were isolated as previously described (59). To
530 summary, the small intestine was dissected at the pyloric sphincter and ileocecal valve. The
531 first 5 cm were considered as duodenum, the remaining proximal half as the jejunum, and the
532 distal part as ileum. Each part was processed independently. After flushing its lumen with ice-
533 cold PBS, the small intestine was open longitudinally, washed three times with PBS, and cut
534 into 2cm pieces. It was then shaken for 20 minutes at 37°C and 80 rpm in Hanks' Balanced Salt
535 solution (HBSS, Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #14170-112) containing 10 mM EDTA. After
536 two washes in ice-cold PBS, tissue enzymatic digestion was performed two times by incubating
537 for 20 minutes at 37°C in dissociating mix (DNase I from bovine pancreas (Roche, Basel,
538 Switzerland, cat. #11284932001), 1 Wünsch unit/mL Liberase TL (Roche, Basel, Switzerland,
539 cat. #05401020001), 2% FBS in HBSS). Finally, the remaining tissue was processed on a 70
540 µm cell strainer, the samples washed two times, and stained for flow cytometry.

541 Mandibular and gut-draining lymph nodes were dissected, incubated for 20 minutes at 37°C in
542 digestion mix (10 mM hepes, 5% FBS, 0.2 mg/mL Collagenase D (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis,
543 MO, USA, cat. #11088858001) in HBSS), and smashed on 40 µm cell strainers with syringe
544 plungers. Spleens were directly smashed on 70 µm cell strainers, the erythrocytes lysed with
545 ACK lysis buffer (155 mM ammonium chloride, 10 mM potassium bicarbonate, 0.1 mM EDTA
546 in distilled water, pH adjusted to 7.2-7.4), and subsequently filtered through 40 µm cell
547 strainers. Samples were washed one time and stained for flow cytometry analysis.

548

549 **Statistical analysis**

550 For all experiments using human primary cells, each replicate was a unique healthy donor. For
551 experiments involving mice, each replicate was a single mouse, except for the small intestine
552 flow cytometry analysis, where both the duodenum and jejunum parts of each mouse were
553 separately considered as technical replicates. The GraphPad Prism 10 software was used for the
554 analysis. The statistical method for each test is provided in the corresponding figure legend. P-
555 value corresponding symbols are * $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, *** $P \leq 0.001$, **** $P \leq 0.0001$.
556 Normal distribution was assumed for all sample means. No outliers were excluded.

557

558 List of supplementary materials:

559 Materials and methods

560 Fig. S1 to S16

561 Tables S1 to S4 (Excel file)

562 References (60–67)

563

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565 **General**

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580 **Author contributions**

581 Conceptualization/Supervision: Y.D.M

582 Designed experiments: R.P., J.B.L., Y.D.M

583 Performed experiments: R.P., A.A.S., B.P., M.H., J.B.L., O.A.A., L.E., R.C., E.L., E.P.

584 Analyzed data: R.P., Y.D.M.

585 Provided reagents and advice: J.B.L., F.D.P., D.G., D.V., D.M., J.E., Q.T., T.V.P., G.C., M.I.,
586 C.P., G.P., L.M.S.

587 Wrote the original draft: R.P., L.M.S, Y.D.M.

588 Reviewed and edited the manuscript: all

589 All authors approved the manuscript.

590

591 **Conflicts of interest**

592 J.E. owns stocks in Mnemo Therapeutics and Cytovia Therapeutics. J.E. is a compensated
593 scientific advisor for Enterome, Treefrog Therapeutics and Resolution Therapeutics. Q.T. is a
594 co-founder, shareholder, and scientific advisor of Sonoma Biotherapeutics. Q.T. is a consultant
595 of eGenesis and Qihan Bio. Q.T. is a coinventor of the following patents: “Expansion of
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604 declare conflicts of interest.

605

606 **Data and materials availability**

607 All data related to this study are available in the main text or the supplementary materials. The
608 corresponding authors will make available upon request the raw data supporting the conclusions
609 of this work, without undue reservation.

610

611 Figure legends:

612 **Fig. 1. Five gluten-specific TCRs were successfully cloned, validated, and integrated into**
613 **the TRAC locus of human primary T cells by HDR.**

614 (A) Gluten-specific TCR sequences selected from (15).

615 (B) Deamidated gliadin-derived peptides used in this study. Nine-core epitopes are shown in
616 red (glia- α 1a) or underlined (glia- α 2).

617 (C) Experimental design for the TCR screening platform using mRNA transfection into β 2m
618 KO TCR KO NFAT-Luciferase CD4⁺ Jurkat cells.

619 (D) Representative flow cytometry plots showing CD3 and TCR expression after
620 mRNA transfection (gated on CD4⁺ living cells).

621 (E) Luminescence signal 18 hours after co-culture (n = 3).

622 (F) TCR editing strategy into the TRAC locus of human primary T cells.

623 (G) Experimental design

624 (H) Representative CD3 expression in engineered CD4⁺ T cells after seven days of culture.

625 (I) Cumulative percentage of CD3⁻ (KO) and CD3⁺ (S2, LS2.8, D2, JR5.1, S16) expression
626 after seven days of culture (n = 6).

627 (J) Expansion of UTD and engineered T cells (n = 6).

628 (K) Representative CD25 and CD71 expression after 48-hours co-culture (gated on living
629 CD4⁺CD3⁺ cells).

630 (L) Cumulative data showing. Each engineered condition was compared to the UTD one (n =
631 6). Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. Two-way ANOVA was used for the statistic.

632 Abbreviations. AAV6, adeno-associated virus type 6; APC, antigen-presenting cell; CDR3,
633 complementary-determining region 3; Chr, chromosome; HA, homology arm; Km, Michaelis-
634 Menten kinetics constant; TRBD, T cell receptor beta diversity; TRAJ, T cell receptor alpha
635 joining; TRBJ, T cell receptor beta joining; TRAV, T cell receptor alpha variable; TRBV, T
636 cell receptor beta variable; UTD, untransduced.

637 **Fig. 2. Peptide dose-response stimulation of gluten-specific engineered T cells**
638 (A) CD4⁺ and (B) CD8⁺ T cells. Percentage of CD25 and CD71 co-expression at each peptide
639 concentration, normalized by the corresponding positive control stimulated with α CD3/28
640 beads. CI, confidence interval. Non-linear least squares regression model based on independent
641 experiments using cells manufactured from three to six different donors.
642
643

644 **Fig. 3. Antigen-specific CD4⁺ eTeffs proliferate in the gut-draining lymph nodes and**
645 **infiltrate the small intestine lamina propria following gliadin oral gavage**

646 (A) Maps of the AAV6 gene cassette used to engineer primary T cells from Cas9 transgenic
647 mice.

648 (B) Experimental design

649 (C) Representative CD3 and GFP expression in engineered CD4⁺ T cells.

650 (D) Percentage of CD3⁻ (KO) and CD3⁺GFP⁺ (S2, D2) on CD4⁺ T cells after expansion (n = 5-
651 11).

652 (E) Expansion rate of CD4⁺ T cells.

653 (F) Representative CD25 and CD69 expression in CD4⁺ T cells after overnight co-culture with
654 HLA-DQ2.5⁺ BMDCs pulsed with different peptides at 5 μM.

655 (G) Cumulative data. Each T cell population was compared to the UTD one (n = 6-10).

656 (H) Peptide-dose response stimulation representing CD25⁺CD69⁺ co-expression on CD4⁺ T
657 cells following activation assay, normalized by the corresponding positive control stimulated
658 with αCD3ε-pulsed HLA-DQ2.5⁺ BMDCs (n = 6).

659 (I) AAV and RV gene cassette designs.

660 (J) Phenotype of engineered CD4⁺ T cells before ACT.

661 (K) Experimental design. 2x10⁶ Thy1.1⁺CD3⁺CD4⁺ eTeffs were injected intravenously in
662 DQ2.5⁺ C57BL/6 mice. Mice were kept either under a gluten-free or standard diet, and received
663 oral gavage with PBS or 0.5 mg gliadin-α₃₃mer on D1 after ACT.

664 (L) Bioluminescence over time of one independent experiment.

665 (M) Schematic of the abdominal region of interest (ROI) delimitation and corresponding
666 cumulative data showing bioluminescent signal for each diet/gavage combinations on days two
667 and four after ACT (n = 3-5 per group, one experiment).

668 (N) Schematic of the anatomical localization of each gut segment and their corresponding
669 draining LNs (Ce, D, J, I, Ac, C) (adapted from (21)) and the mandibular (Ma) LNs. Circles
670 represent the LNs, and the connected lines represent their draining pathways. Scale bars, 5 mm.

671 (O) Experimental design. 2x10⁶ GFP⁺CTV⁺CD4⁺ eTeffs were adoptively transferred into
672 DQ2.5⁺ C57BL/6 mice that received 0.5 mg gliadin-α₃₃mer one day later by oral gavage. Organs
673 were harvested on day 5 after ACT for analysis.

674 (P) Representative CTV dilution. GFP⁺ CD4⁺ eTeffs are in red and non-edited CD4⁺ T cells in
675 black.

676 (Q) Division index of S2 CD4⁺ eTeffs in different LNs compared to the spleen (n = 4).

677 (R) Cumulative data for CTV MFI of S2 CD4⁺ eTeffs in the small intestine (duodenum,
678 jejunum, and ileum), the gut-draining LNs (L-, Ce-, D- J-, I-, Ac-, C-, and Ma-LNs), and the
679 spleen (n = 4).

680 (S) CCR9 and α4β7 expression in engineered S2 (red) compared to non-edited (black) CD4⁺
681 eTeffs (n = 4).

682 Abbreviations. Ac, ascendant colon; ACT, adoptive cell transfer; BMDC, bone marrow-derived
683 dendritic cells; C, colon; Ce, celiac; D, duodenum; gdLNs, gut-draining lymph nodes; GF,
684 gluten-free; HDRt, homology-directed repair template; I, ileum; J, jejunum; L, liver; LN, lymph
685 node; Ma, mandibular; sgRNA, single guide RNA; SI, small intestine.

686 Statistics. Data shown are from three (B-H) and two (J-S) independent experiments. Data are
687 presented as mean ± SEM. Panels (G), (M), and (S): two-way ANOVA. Panel (H): non-linear
688 least squares regression model. Panels (Q) and (R): one-way ANOVA.

689 **Fig. 4. Histological analysis of gluten-reactive CD4⁺ eTeff accumulation and interactions**
690 **in vivo**

691 (A) Experimental design. 2×10^6 S2-GFP⁺CD4⁺ eTeffs were adoptively transferred into B6-
692 DQ2.5 mice. Oral gavage with 0.5 mg gli α _33mer was performed one day later, and organs
693 were harvested five days later for cryo-embedding.

694 (B) Representative histological section of the jejunum Swiss roll stained with hematoxylin and
695 eosin (left), and gut compartmentalization for the analysis (villi (orange), crypts (blue), and
696 Peyer's patches (green)). Scale bars, 1 mm (left), 200 μ m (right).

697 (C) Representative immunofluorescence images of GFP (green), CD3 (gray), CD4 (red), and
698 DAPI (blue) expression in the duodenum (top) and P-P (bottom) five days after ACT. Scale
699 bars, 50 μ m.

700 (D) Number of GFP⁺ cells per mm² of tissue encountered in the small intestine, M-LNs, and P-
701 P comparing mice comparing oral gavage with PBS or gliadin (n = 5).

702 (E) Number of GFP⁺ cells within in the crypt versus villi of the small intestine, and in the P-P
703 versus M-LNs of the lymphoid organs (P-P versus M-LNs) in mice exposed to gliadin.

704 (F) Number of GFP⁺ cells within the T- and B-cell zones of M-LNs and P-P (n = 5).

705 (G) Representative immunofluorescence images of GFP (green), B220 (red), CD11c (gray),
706 and DAPI (blue) expression in a M-LN. The dotted yellow line indicates the distinction between
707 the T cell and B cell zones. Scale bar, 200 μ m.

708 (H) Ratio of GFP⁺ cells in the B-cell zone to the T cell zone, comparing mice exposed to PBS
709 or gliadin (n=5).

710 (I) Representative immunofluorescence images of GFP (green), B220 (red), CD11c (gray), and
711 DAPI (blue) expression in a M-LN, highlighting CD4⁺ eTeff interactions with either B220⁺ B
712 cells (left) or CD11c⁺ DCs (right). Scale bars, 20 μ m.

713 (J) Bar plots comparing the percentage of GFP⁺ cells interacting with CD11c⁺ DCs (white) to
714 those interacting with B220⁺ B cells (red) in the small intestine, M-LNs, and P-P (n = 5).

715 (K) 2×10^6 S2-GFP⁺CD4⁺CTV⁺ T cells were adoptively transferred into B6-DQ2.5 mice 14 days
716 after anti-CD20 or control isotype monoclonal antibody intravenous injection. Mice received
717 0.5 mg gli α _33mer oral gavage one day after ACT, and were sacrificed five days after ACT
718 for analysis. Histograms and bar plots showing the mean fluorescence intensity (SI, M-LN,
719 spleen) and replication index (M-LN) of S2 eTeffs (n = 4-5).

720 (L) Representative immunofluorescence images of GFP (green), PECAM (red), VEGFR3
721 (gray), and DAPI (blue) expression in a small intestine (left) and M-LN (right), highlighting
722 CD4⁺ eTeff interactions with either PECAM⁺ blood vessels (left) or VEGFR3⁺PECAM⁺
723 lymphatic vessels (right). Scale bars, 20 μ m.

724 (M) Bar plots comparing the percentage of GFP⁺ cells interacting with VEGFR3⁺PECAM⁺
725 lymphatic vessels (white) to those interacting with PECAM⁺ blood vessels (red) in the small
726 intestine, M-LNs, and P-P (n=4).

727 Abbreviations. B-Z, B cell zone; DCs, dendritic cells; M-LN, mesenteric lymph nodes; P-P,
728 Peyer's patches; T-Z, T cell zone.

729 Statistics. Data shown are from a single experiment. Each dot represents a single animal. The
730 analysis of M-LNs for each mouse was based on the average data from two to three LNs. In
731 panels (D), (H), and (K), data are presented as mean \pm SEM, and unpaired t tests were used for
732 comparisons. For panels (E), (F), (J), and (M), paired data are represented for each mouse, and
733 paired t tests were used for comparisons.

734 **Fig. 5. High TCR functional activity enhances suppression of eTregs in a peptide-**
735 **dependent manner**
736 (A) Experimental design for human Tregs
737 (B) Representative CD25⁺CD127^{low} expression during the different isolation steps
738 (C) Representative TCR expression on day 7 after stimulation.
739 (D) Cumulative data showing the editing efficacy defined by the TCR expression.
740 (E) Expansion of eTregs over 12 days of culture.
741 (F) Representative Helios and Foxp3 expression in CD4⁺ Teff and eTregs after expansion.
742 (G) Cumulative data representing the percentage of Foxp3 expression (left) and Foxp3/Helios
743 co-expression (right) of eTregs after 12 days of culture.
744 (H) Schematic, representative and cumulative data of suppression assays comparing polyclonal,
745 antigen-specific and -unspecific eTregs co-cultured with CFSE⁺ eTeffs, HLA-DQ2.5⁺ APCs,
746 pulsed with 1 μM of the glia-α1a (top) or glia-α2 (bottom) peptide.
747 (I) Low (S2) versus high (D2) functional activity-mediated suppression in same-co-culture
748 condition but pulsed with 1 μM of the glia-α2-1a peptide.
749 (J) Polyspecific suppression assay. S2 and D2 eTeffs were CFSE-labeled and mixed together
750 and stimulated with both glia-α1a and glia-α2 peptides at a 1:1 ratio (1 μM each) in the presence
751 of S2, D2 or S2 and D2 eTregs.
752 Abbreviations. AAV, adeno-associated virus; eTCR, engineered TCR; Teff, effector T cell;
753 UTD, untransduced.
754 Statistics. In all panels, data are presented as mean ± SEM of three independent experiments
755 using cells manufactured from three different donors. For panels (H), (I), and (J): two-way
756 ANOVA.

757 **Fig. 6. Gluten-specific murine eTregs suppress CD4⁺ eTeff proliferation in the M-LN and**
758 **inhibit their migration into the small intestine**
759 (A) Representative flow cytometry plots showing the gating strategy for sorting CD4⁺CD25⁺
760 murine Treg.
761 (B) Representative CD3 expression (gated on living CD4⁺ cells) after 6 or 7 days of culture
762 (C) Representative CD25 and Foxp3 expression after 6 or 7 days of culture
763 (D) Expansion of murine UTD and eTregs.
764 (E) Editing strategy used for panel G to I.
765 (F) Experimental condition for panels G to I. 0.5 x 10⁶ Thy1.1⁺ S2 eTeffs were adoptively
766 transferred into B6-DQ2.5 mice either alone, or together with 0.5 x 10⁶ UTD or engineered S2
767 Tregs. Oral gavage with 0.5 mg gli α -33mer was performed one day later, and organs were
768 harvested five days later for analysis.
769 (G) Gating strategy used to identify S2 CD4⁺ eTeff *ex vivo*.
770 (H) Representative CFSE dilution of Thy1.1⁺CD4⁺ eTeff in the small intestine comparing no
771 Tregs, UTD Tregs or S2 eTregs.
772 (I) Mean fluorescence intensity cumulative data of Thy1.1⁺CD4⁺ eTeffs in the SI, M-LN, and
773 spleen, measured by CFSE dilution.
774 (J) Editing strategy used for panel K to L.
775 (K) Gating strategy used to identify S2 (Thy1.1⁺) and D2 (GFP^{high}) CD4⁺ eTeffs *ex vivo*
776 (L) S2, D2 or S2 and D2 engineered murine Tregs were co-injected with CTV⁺ polyspecific
777 (D2+S2) CD4⁺ eTeffs. Mice received 0.5 mg gli α -33mer one day later, and organs were
778 harvested five days later for analysis. Bar plots showing the percentage and mean fluorescence
779 intensity of S2 and D2 eTeffs among CD4⁺ cells in the SI, M-LN and the spleen.
780 Abbreviations. M-LN, mesenteric lymph node; SI, small intestine; Teff, effector T cell; UTD,
781 untransduced.
782 (M) D2 engineered murine Tregs were co-injected with CTV⁺ polyspecific (D2+W321) CD4⁺
783 eTeffs. Mice received both 0.5 mg gli α -33mer and 0.5 mg gli ω -34mer peptides by
784 intragastric gavage one day after ACT and were sacrificed five days after ACT. Bar plots
785 showing the percentage and mean fluorescence intensity of D2 and W321 eTeffs among CD4⁺
786 cells in the SI, M-LN and the spleen.
787 Statistics. For each suppression assay settings, data shown are from two (L) or one (M)
788 independent experiments. In all panels, data are presented as mean \pm SEM. For panel (I): one-
789 way ANOVA. For panels (L-M): two-way ANOVA.
790

791 References:

- 792
- 793 1. K. Kurppa, C. J. Mulder, K. Stordal, K. Kaukinen, Celiac Disease Affects 1% of Global
794 Population: Who Will Manage All These Patients? *Gastroenterology* **167**, 148-158
795 (2024).
- 796 2. R. Iversen, L. M. Sollid, The Immunobiology and Pathogenesis of Celiac Disease. *Annu*
797 *Rev Pathol* **18**, 47-70 (2023).
- 798 3. L. M. Sollid, The roles of MHC class II genes and post-translational modification in
799 celiac disease. *Immunogenetics* **69**, 605-616 (2017).
- 800 4. K. E. Lundin *et al.*, Gliadin-specific, HLA-DQ(alpha 1*0501,beta 1*0201) restricted T
801 cells isolated from the small intestinal mucosa of celiac disease patients. *J Exp Med* **178**,
802 187-196 (1993).
- 803 5. M. Crepaldi *et al.*, Emerging Pharmaceutical Therapies to Address the Inadequacy of a
804 Gluten-Free Diet for Celiac Disease. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)* **17**, (2023).
- 805 6. S. R. Bozorg, A. R. Lee, K. Mårild, J. A. Murray, The Economic Iceberg of Celiac
806 Disease: More Than the Cost of Gluten-Free Food. *Gastroenterology* **167**, 172-182
807 (2024).
- 808 7. K. E. Lundin *et al.*, Understanding celiac disease monitoring patterns and outcomes
809 after diagnosis: A multinational, retrospective chart review study. *World J*
810 *Gastroenterol* **27**, 2603-2614 (2021).
- 811 8. N. Patel *et al.*, Clinical Data Do Not Reliably Predict Duodenal Histology at Follow-up
812 in Celiac Disease: A 13 Center Correlative Study. *Am J Surg Pathol* **48**, 212-220 (2024).
- 813 9. L. M. Sollid, Tolerance-inducing therapies in coeliac disease - mechanisms, progress
814 and future directions. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol* **21**, 335-347 (2024).
- 815 10. L. M. R. Ferreira, Y. D. Muller, J. A. Bluestone, Q. Tang, Next-generation regulatory
816 T cell therapy. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* **18**, 749-769 (2019).
- 817 11. J. H. Esensten, Y. D. Muller, J. A. Bluestone, Q. Tang, Regulatory T-cell therapy for
818 autoimmune and autoinflammatory diseases: The next frontier. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*
819 **142**, 1710-1718 (2018).
- 820 12. C. Raffin, L. T. Vo, J. A. Bluestone, T(reg) cell-based therapies: challenges and
821 perspectives. *Nat Rev Immunol* **20**, 158-172 (2020).
- 822 13. L. M. Sollid *et al.*, Update 2020: nomenclature and listing of celiac disease-relevant
823 gluten epitopes recognized by CD4(+) T cells. *Immunogenetics* **72**, 85-88 (2020).
- 824 14. J. A. Tye-Din *et al.*, Comprehensive, quantitative mapping of T cell epitopes in gluten
825 in celiac disease. *Sci Transl Med* **2**, 41ra51 (2010).
- 826 15. J. Petersen *et al.*, T-cell receptor recognition of HLA-DQ2-gliadin complexes associated
827 with celiac disease. *Nat Struct Mol Biol* **21**, 480-488 (2014).

- 828 16. Y. D. Muller *et al.*, Precision Engineering of an Anti-HLA-A2 Chimeric Antigen
829 Receptor in Regulatory T Cells for Transplant Immune Tolerance. *Front Immunol* **12**,
830 686439 (2021).
- 831 17. W. A. Nyberg *et al.*, An evolved AAV variant enables efficient genetic engineering of
832 murine T cells. *Cell* **186**, 446-460 e419 (2023).
- 833 18. J. Eyquem *et al.*, Targeting a CAR to the TRAC locus with CRISPR/Cas9 enhances
834 tumour rejection. *Nature* **543**, 113-117 (2017).
- 835 19. L. Shan *et al.*, Structural basis for gluten intolerance in celiac sprue. *Science* **297**, 2275-
836 2279 (2002).
- 837 20. S. W. Qiao *et al.*, Antigen presentation to celiac lesion-derived T cells of a 33-mer
838 gliadin peptide naturally formed by gastrointestinal digestion. *J Immunol* **173**, 1757-
839 1762 (2004).
- 840 21. H. Brown, M. R. Komnick, P. H. Bringleb, T. S. Dermody, D. Esterhazy, Lymph node
841 sharing between pancreas, gut, and liver leads to immune crosstalk and regulation of
842 pancreatic autoimmunity. *Immunity* **56**, 2070-2085 e2011 (2023).
- 843 22. S. Dahal-Koirala *et al.*, Discriminative T-cell receptor recognition of highly
844 homologous HLA-DQ2-bound gluten epitopes. *J Biol Chem* **294**, 941-952 (2019).
- 845 23. T. Takahashi *et al.*, Immunologic self-tolerance maintained by CD25+CD4+ naturally
846 anergic and suppressive T cells: induction of autoimmune disease by breaking their
847 anergic/suppressive state. *Int Immunol* **10**, 1969-1980 (1998).
- 848 24. G. Plesa *et al.*, TCR affinity and specificity requirements for human regulatory T-cell
849 function. *Blood* **119**, 3420-3430 (2012).
- 850 25. A. Christophersen *et al.*, Healthy HLA-DQ2.5+ Subjects Lack Regulatory and Memory
851 T Cells Specific for Immunodominant Gluten Epitopes of Celiac Disease. *J Immunol*
852 **196**, 2819-2826 (2016).
- 853 26. M. Ben Ahmed *et al.*, IL-15 renders conventional lymphocytes resistant to suppressive
854 functions of regulatory T cells through activation of the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase
855 pathway. *J Immunol* **182**, 6763-6770 (2009).
- 856 27. L. Cook *et al.*, Circulating gluten-specific FOXP3(+)CD39(+) regulatory T cells have
857 impaired suppressive function in patients with celiac disease. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*
858 **140**, 1592-1603 e1598 (2017).
- 859 28. V. Abadie *et al.*, IL-15, gluten and HLA-DQ8 drive tissue destruction in coeliac disease.
860 *Nature* **578**, 600-604 (2020).
- 861 29. M. Tiittanen, M. Westerholm-Ormio, M. Verkasalo, E. Savilahti, O. Vaarala,
862 Infiltration of forkhead box P3-expressing cells in small intestinal mucosa in coeliac
863 disease but not in type 1 diabetes. *Clin Exp Immunol* **152**, 498-507 (2008).

- 864 30. T. Vorobjova *et al.*, Increased FOXP3 expression in small-bowel mucosa of children
865 with coeliac disease and type I diabetes mellitus. *Scand J Gastroenterol* **44**, 422-430
866 (2009).
- 867 31. Y. D. Muller *et al.*, Anti-CD154 mAb and rapamycin induce T regulatory cell mediated
868 tolerance in rat-to-mouse islet transplantation. *PLoS One* **5**, e10352 (2010).
- 869 32. N. B. Hmida *et al.*, Impaired control of effector T cells by regulatory T cells: a clue to
870 loss of oral tolerance and autoimmunity in celiac disease? *Am J Gastroenterol* **107**, 604-
871 611 (2012).
- 872 33. Q. Tang *et al.*, In vitro-expanded antigen-specific regulatory T cells suppress
873 autoimmune diabetes. *J Exp Med* **199**, 1455-1465 (2004).
- 874 34. J. E. Chang, M. B. Buechler, E. Gressier, S. J. Turley, M. C. Carroll, Mechanosensing
875 by Peyer's patch stroma regulates lymphocyte migration and mucosal antibody
876 responses. *Nat Immunol* **20**, 1506-1516 (2019).
- 877 35. R. Bartolome-Casado *et al.*, CD4(+) T cells persist for years in the human small intestine
878 and display a T(H)1 cytokine profile. *Mucosal Immunol* **14**, 402-410 (2021).
- 879 36. R. Di Niro *et al.*, High abundance of plasma cells secreting transglutaminase 2-specific
880 IgA autoantibodies with limited somatic hypermutation in celiac disease intestinal
881 lesions. *Nature Medicine* **18**, 441-445 (2012).
- 882 37. V. Abadie, A. S. Han, B. Jabri, L. M. Sollid, New Insights on Genes, Gluten, and
883 Immunopathogenesis of Celiac Disease. *Gastroenterology* **167**, 4-22 (2024).
- 884 38. J. Y. Tsang *et al.*, The potency of allospecific Tregs cells appears to correlate with T
885 cell receptor functional avidity. *Am J Transplant* **11**, 1610-1620 (2011).
- 886 39. W. I. Yeh *et al.*, Avidity and Bystander Suppressive Capacity of Human Regulatory T
887 Cells Expressing De Novo Autoreactive T-Cell Receptors in Type 1 Diabetes. *Front*
888 *Immunol* **8**, 1313 (2017).
- 889 40. B. Liu *et al.*, A Hybrid Insulin Epitope Maintains High 2D Affinity for Diabetogenic T
890 Cells in the Periphery. *Diabetes* **69**, 381-391 (2020).
- 891 41. D. A. Schmid *et al.*, Evidence for a TCR affinity threshold delimiting maximal CD8 T
892 cell function. *J Immunol* **184**, 4936-4946 (2010).
- 893 42. G. Mazzarella *et al.*, Gliadin activates HLA class I-restricted CD8+ T cells in celiac
894 disease intestinal mucosa and induces the enterocyte apoptosis. *Gastroenterology* **134**,
895 1017-1027 (2008).
- 896 43. M. Bodd *et al.*, Direct cloning and tetramer staining to measure the frequency of
897 intestinal gluten-reactive T cells in celiac disease. *Eur J Immunol* **43**, 2605-2612 (2013).
- 898 44. S. Hue *et al.*, A direct role for NKG2D/MICA interaction in villous atrophy during
899 celiac disease. *Immunity* **21**, 367-377 (2004).

- 900 45. B. Meresse *et al.*, Coordinated induction by IL15 of a TCR-independent NKG2D
901 signaling pathway converts CTL into lymphokine-activated killer cells in celiac disease.
902 *Immunity* **21**, 357-366 (2004).
- 903 46. P. Hoffmann *et al.*, Loss of FOXP3 expression in natural human CD4+CD25+
904 regulatory T cells upon repetitive in vitro stimulation. *European Journal of Immunology*
905 **39**, 1088-1097 (2009).
- 906 47. A. E. Mahne, J. E. Klementowicz, A. Chou, V. Nguyen, Q. Tang, Therapeutic
907 regulatory T cells subvert effector T cell function in inflamed islets to halt autoimmune
908 diabetes. *J Immunol* **194**, 3147-3155 (2015).
- 909 48. A. E. Dewan, F. Koentgen, M. K. Johannesen, M. F. du Pre, L. M. Sollid, Generation
910 of an HLA-DQ2.5 Knock-In Mouse. *Immunohorizons* **5**, 25-32 (2021).
- 911 49. V. T. Chu *et al.*, Efficient generation of Rosa26 knock-in mice using CRISPR/Cas9 in
912 C57BL/6 zygotes. *BMC Biotechnol* **16**, 4 (2016).
- 913 50. J. C. Grieger, V. W. Choi, R. J. Samulski, Production and characterization of adeno-
914 associated viral vectors. *Nat Protoc* **1**, 1412-1428 (2006).
- 915 51. T. Matsushita *et al.*, Adeno-associated virus vectors can be efficiently produced without
916 helper virus. *Gene Ther* **5**, 938-945 (1998).
- 917 52. M. J. Yousefzadeh *et al.*, Mechanism of suppression of chromosomal instability by
918 DNA polymerase POLQ. *PLoS Genet* **10**, e1004654 (2014).
- 919 53. P. Ho, C. Ede, Y. Y. Chen, Modularly Constructed Synthetic Granzyme B Molecule
920 Enables Interrogation of Intracellular Proteases for Targeted Cytotoxicity. *ACS Synth*
921 *Biol* **6**, 1484-1495 (2017).
- 922 54. E. Lanitis *et al.*, Optimized gene engineering of murine CAR-T cells reveals the
923 beneficial effects of IL-15 coexpression. *J Exp Med* **218**, (2021).
- 924 55. S. Lin, B. T. Staahl, R. K. Alla, J. A. Doudna, Enhanced homology-directed human
925 genome engineering by controlled timing of CRISPR/Cas9 delivery. *Elife* **3**, e04766
926 (2014).
- 927 56. C. A. Vakulskas *et al.*, A high-fidelity Cas9 mutant delivered as a ribonucleoprotein
928 complex enables efficient gene editing in human hematopoietic stem and progenitor
929 cells. *Nat Med* **24**, 1216-1224 (2018).
- 930 57. D. N. Nguyen *et al.*, Polymer-stabilized Cas9 nanoparticles and modified repair
931 templates increase genome editing efficiency. *Nat Biotechnol* **38**, 44-49 (2020).
- 932 58. T. L. Roth *et al.*, Reprogramming human T cell function and specificity with non-viral
933 genome targeting. *Nature* **559**, 405-409 (2018).
- 934 59. D. Duc *et al.*, Disrupting Myelin-Specific Th17 Cell Gut Homing Confers Protection in
935 an Adoptive Transfer Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis. *Cell Rep* **29**, 378-
936 390.e374 (2019).

- 937 60. D. Conant *et al.*, Inference of CRISPR Edits from Sanger Trace Data. *CRISPR J* **5**, 123-
938 130 (2022).
- 939 61. A. Corona *et al.*, Cynarin blocks Ebola virus replication by counteracting VP35
940 inhibition of interferon-beta production. *Antiviral Res* **198**, 105251 (2022).
- 941 62. A. Alcaraz-Serna *et al.*, Immune synapse instructs epigenomic and transcriptomic
942 functional reprogramming in dendritic cells. *Sci Adv* **7**, (2021).
- 943 63. C. B. Lindstad *et al.*, Characterization of T-cell receptor transgenic mice recognizing
944 immunodominant HLA-DQ2.5-restricted gluten epitopes. *Eur J Immunol* **51**, 1002-
945 1005 (2021).
- 946 64. J. Uchida *et al.*, The innate mononuclear phagocyte network depletes B lymphocytes
947 through Fc receptor-dependent mechanisms during anti-CD20 antibody
948 immunotherapy. *J Exp Med* **199**, 1659-1669 (2004).
- 949 65. P. Bankhead *et al.*, QuPath: Open source software for digital pathology image analysis.
950 *Sci Rep* **7**, 16878 (2017).
- 951 66. U. Schmidt, M. Weigert, C. Broaddus, G. Myers, in *Medical Image Computing and*
952 *Computer Assisted Intervention–MICCAI 2018: 21st International Conference,*
953 *Granada, Spain, September 16-20, 2018, Proceedings, Part II 11.* (Springer, 2018), pp.
954 265-273.
- 955 67. D. A. Vignali, J. Moreno, D. Schiller, G. J. Hammerling, Species-specific binding of
956 CD4 to the beta 2 domain of major histocompatibility complex class II molecules. *J Exp*
957 *Med* **175**, 925-932 (1992).
958

Figure 1

Figure 2

A CD4 Teff

B CD8 Teff

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

1 Supplementary materials and methods:

2 **Cell line generation**

3 NFAT-Luciferase Jurkat cells were obtained from BPS Bioscience Inc (San Diego, CA). The
4 beta constant region of the TCR (TRBC) was edited and CD3 negative cells were further
5 purified. A KO of the TRAC gene was thereafter performed. Single cells were plated, and
6 clones were screened for indel insertions in the TRAC locus. Editing was confirmed by sanger
7 sequencing and the ICE CRISPR Analysis Tool (Synthego, Redwood City, CA, USA) (60).
8 One clone was selected and transduced with the human CD4 gene cloned into a lentivirus and
9 further sorted for high CD4 expression. The β 2m Raji cell line was generated by editing the
10 β 2m gene in wild-type Raji cells. The K-64.86 cell line was produced by transducing CD64
11 and CD86 genes into the wild-type K562 cell line and were further FACS sorted.

12

13 **Gluten-derived peptides**

14 Peptides used in this study were all synthesized by the Peptide and Tetramer Core Facility of
15 the Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research in Lausanne. Deamidated peptide sequences are
16 specified in Table S2. Glia- α _33mer and glia- ω _34mer were resuspended in PBS at 5 mg/mL,
17 whereas glia- α 1a, glia- α 2, and glia- ω 1 were resuspended in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO,
18 Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA, cat. #D2650) at 10 mM. Aliquots were kept at -80°C.

19

20 **Flow cytometry**

21 For flow cytometry analysis, cells were stained for 30 minutes at 4°C, washed with FACS buffer
22 (PBS 0.5% FBS and 2 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, Invitrogen, Waltham, MA,
23 USA, Cat. #AM9261)), and resuspended in FACS buffer containing DAPI at 1:2000 dilution.
24 For staining of murine cells, Fc Block was added to the mix of antibodies at a 1:200 dilution.
25 For staining of murine peripheral blood, cells were lastly incubated for 15 minutes in a lysing

26 solution (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA, Cat. #349202) at a 1:10 dilution in water.
27 For intracellular staining, cells were stained for 30 minutes at 4°C with extracellular antibodies,
28 including live/dead marker (Phantom dye, 1:1000 dilution). Then, cells were fixed with a
29 Foxp3/transcription factor staining buffer set (Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, USA, Cat. #00-5523-
30 00.). Cells were washed two times with FACS buffer and incubated in 150 µL of 1x Fix/Perm
31 buffer at 4°C. Then, cells were centrifuged, washed once with 1x Permeabilization buffer, and
32 incubated for 30 minutes in 1x Permeabilization buffer containing intracellular staining
33 antibodies. Finally, cells were washed and resuspended in FACS buffer. Samples were analyzed
34 on a BD LSR Fortessa Cell Analyzer (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA), and data
35 were processed with FlowJo v10.9.0 software (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA)

36

37 **In vitro luciferase assay**

38 Luciferase assay was conducted as previously described (61). Cells were first collected and
39 lysed for 20 minutes by shaking at 300 rpm with 50 µL harvesting buffer (50 mM 2-
40 morpholinoethanesulfonic acid sodium (MES, pH 7.8, Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA,
41 cat. #1061970100), 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.8), 1 mM dithiothreitol (Thermo Fisher Scientific,
42 Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #R0861) + 0.2% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham,
43 MA, USA, Cat. #9002-93-1) in distilled water). Then, 50 µL of luciferase buffer (125 mM
44 MES, 125 Tris-HCl (pH 7.8), 25 mM magnesium acetate tetrahydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-
45 Louis, MO, USA, cat. #M0631), 2.5 mM adenosine triphosphate (ATP, Thermo Fisher
46 Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #R0441) in distilled water) was added to the lysate and
47 shaken for one minute. Finally, 50 µL of luciferin buffer (1 mM D-luciferin (Thermo Fisher
48 Scientific, Waltham, USA, cat. #88292) in 5 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate (Merck,
49 Darmstadt, Germany, cat. #1.04873)) was added to the lysate, and luminescence was measured
50 8-10 minutes after on a Synergy H1 Hybrid reader (BioTek, Winooski, VT, USA).

51

52 **Primary T cell expansion**

53 Human primary cells were activated with K-64.86 cells (1:2 K:T cell ratio) and anti-CD3
54 purified antibody (1 µg/mL, clone OKT3, BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA, cat.
55 #566685), and cultured for two days in X-Vivo 15 medium (Lonza, Basel, Switzerland, Cat.
56 #02-053Q) supplemented with 5% human type AB serum from male donor (Pan-Biotech,
57 Aidenbach, Germany, Cat. #P30-2901), 1% penicillin-streptomycin (BioConcept, Allschwill,
58 Switzerland, Cat. #4-01F00-H), 55 µM 2-mercaptoethanol (Gibco, Grand Island, NY, USA,
59 Cat. #21985-023), and 10 mM N-acetyl-L-cysteine (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA,
60 Cat. #A9165-25G). After electroporation, cells were switched to a serum-free medium for AAV
61 transduction. The next day cells were cultured in Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI)
62 medium (Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA, Cat. #61870-010) supplemented with 10% FBS (Sigma-
63 Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA, cat. #F7524), 1% non-essential amino acids (NEAA, Gibco,
64 Grand Island, NY, USA, cat. #11140-050), 10 mM hepes buffer solution (Gibco, Paisley, UK,
65 cat. #15630-056), 1 mM sodium pyruvate (Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #11360-039), and
66 1% penicillin-streptomycin. Medium was supplemented with 30 IU/mL recombinant human
67 IL-2 (rhIL-2, Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany, Cat. #130-097-746) (effector T
68 cells), or 300 IU/mL rhIL-2 (Tregs). Tregs were re-stimulated on day 7 of expansion with anti-
69 human CD3/CD28 Dynabeads (Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA, Cat. #11131D) at 1:1 bead:Treg
70 ratio.

71 Murine CD4⁺ T cells were activated with anti-mouseCD3/CD28 Dynabeads (Gibco, Waltham,
72 MA, USA, Cat. #11452D) at a 2:1 (Teff) or 3:1 (Treg) bead:T cell ratio. Effector CD4⁺ T cells
73 were cultured in complete mouse medium, consisting in RPMI complete human medium
74 supplemented with 55 µM 2-mercaptoethanol (Gibco, Grand Island, NY, USA, Cat. #21985-
75 023). Medium was enriched with 50 IU/mL rhIL-2, 5 ng/mL recombinant human IL-7 (rhIL-7,

76 Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany, Cat. # 130-095-362), and 5 ng/mL recombinant
77 human IL-15 (rhIL-15, Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany, Cat. #130-095-764).
78 Murine Tregs were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) – high glucose
79 (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA, Cat. #D5796-1L), supplemented with 10% FBS, 1%
80 NEAA, 0.5 mM sodium pyruvate, 5 mM hepes buffer solution, 1 mM L-glutamine (Sigma-
81 Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA, Cat. #G7513-100ML), 55 μ M 2-mercaptoethanol, 1%
82 penicillin-streptomycin, and 2000 IU/mL rhIL-2.

83 All primary cells were cultured at 37°C with 5% CO₂ and kept at a confluency of 1×10^6
84 cells/mL. Cytokines were renewed every other day. On the day before functional assays, anti-
85 CD3/CD28 beads were removed, and Tregs were rested overnight in complete medium only.

86

87 **Human B cell expansion**

88 The proportion of CD19⁺ B cells was determined from PBMCs and plated at 0.125×10^6
89 cells/mL in X-Vivo 15 medium (Lonza, Basel, Switzerland, Cat. #02-053Q), supplemented
90 with 10% human type AB serum from a male donor (Pan-Biotech, Aidenbach, Germany, Cat.
91 #P30-2901), 75 μ g/mL gentamycin (ThermoFisher, Waltham, MA, USA, Cat. #15750060), and
92 human insulin (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA, cat. #I9278). An equal volume of
93 irradiated (120 Gy) CD40L⁺ K562 cells at 0.5×10^6 cells/mL was added to the B cells, along
94 with 4 ng/mL IL-4 (Miltenyi, Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany, Cat. #170-076-135), 1 μ g/mL
95 cyclosporin (Novartis, Basel, Switzerland, SANDIMMUN conc perf 50 mg/mL), and 5 μ g/mL
96 ganciclovir (Genentech, San Francisco, CA, USA, Cat. #0004-6940-03). On days 2 and 4 of
97 expansion, an equal volume of fresh medium was added with the same concentrations of IL-4,
98 cyclosporin, and ganciclovir. On day 7, cells were counted, phenotyped by flow cytometry, and
99 restimulated at 0.5×10^6 cells/mL with irradiated CD40L⁺ K562 cells at a 1:10 K562:B cell

100 ratio. This restimulation was repeated every three days until day 13. B cells were then
101 cryopreserved.

102

103 **Human MoDC differentiation**

104 Human CD14⁺ cells were enriched from PBMCs with the CD14 MicroBeads system (Miltenyi
105 Biotec, Bergisch-Gladbach, Germany, Cat. #130-050-201) and plated at 1 x 10⁶ cells/mL in
106 RPMI complete human medium supplemented with 50 ng/mL IL-4 (Miltenyi, Bergisch-
107 Gladbach, Germany, Cat. #170-076-135) and 50 ng/mL GM-CSF (R&D systems, Minneapolis,
108 MN, USA, Cat. #215-GM). Cytokines were replenished on day 3. On day 6, cells were collected
109 and plated at 1 x 10⁶ cells/mL with fresh IL-4, GM-CSF, and 10 ng/mL LPS (InvivoGen, San
110 Diego, CA, USA, cat. #tlrl-3pelps) overnight. On day 7, MoDCs were harvested, phenotyped
111 by flow cytometry, and used for functional assays.

112

113 **BMDC differentiation**

114 BMDCs were differentiated as previously described (62). Briefly, bone marrow was collected
115 from B6-DQ2.5 mouse femurs and tibias and cultured in mouse medium supplemented with 20
116 ng/mL GM-CSF (R&D systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA, Cat. # 415-ML). Three days later
117 medium and GM-CSF were renewed. On day six and nine, cells were detached with a cell
118 scraper (Sarstedt, Nümbrecht, Germany, Cat. #101093-452), washed, and plated with fresh
119 medium. On day nine, 250 ng/mL LPS (InvivoGen, San Diego, CA, USA, cat. #tlrl-3pelps) was
120 added overnight to the culture. BMDCs were phenotyped and used freshly for further activation
121 assays or cryopreserved.

122

123 **In vitro activation and proliferation assays**

124 For functional assays involving human primary T cells, 40 Gy-irradiated HLA-DQ2.5+ β 2m
125 KO Raji cells were used as antigen presenting cells (APC). For activation assays, 0.1×10^6 T
126 cells were co-cultured with 0.05×10^6 APCs in each condition. Peptides were added to the co-
127 culture at a final concentration of 5 μ M, when not otherwise specified. After two days of co-
128 culture, cells were harvested and stained for CD25 and CD71 activation markers. Samples were
129 analyzed by flow cytometry. Anti-human CD3/CD28 beads at 1:1 bead:T cell ratio were used
130 as positive control.

131 Murine functional assays were performed with 40 Gy-irradiated BMDCs as APCs. 0.1×10^6
132 CD4+ T cells were co-cultures with 0.02×10^6 BMDCs (1:5 BMDC:T cell ratio) and pulsed with
133 the corresponding peptide. When not otherwise specified, 5 μ M was used for each peptide
134 concentration. Cells were incubated overnight, and harvested to assess CD25 and CD69
135 expression by flow cytometry. Monoclonal anti-CD3 ϵ antibody (clone 145-2C11, Thermo
136 Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #16-0031-82) together with APCs was used at 2
137 μ g/mL as positive control.

138 In proliferation assays, human/murine T cells were stained with 1 μ M CFSE or CTV for 5
139 minutes in PBS at room temperature, and subsequently washed two times and incubated for
140 four days with APCs and peptides. Proliferation was assessed by CFSE/CTV dilution. No
141 cytokines were used for any functional assay.

142

143 **Mouse model for CeD, in vivo cell trafficking, and ex vivo analysis**

144 The adoptive transfer model for gluten-specific T cell proliferation in DQ2.5 B6 mice was
145 previously described (63). Briefly, expanded engineered CD4+ T cells were adoptively
146 transferred by tail intravenous injection. The day after, oral gavage was performed with 100 μ L
147 of PBS or 0.5 mg gliadin- α _33mer or gliadin- ω _34mer reconstituted in 100 μ L of PBS. In the *in vivo*
148 experiments involving D2 and W321 eTeffs, each mouse was given 0.5 mg gliadin- α _33mer and

149 0.5 mg glia- ω _34mer in 200 μ L of PBS by oral gavage. For in vivo trafficking experiments,
150 mice were injected intra-peritoneally with 100 μ L of luciferin (15 mg/mL) and anesthetized in
151 an isoflurane chamber. Eight minutes later, bioluminescence was measured with an IVIS
152 Lumina III in vivo imaging system (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). Images were analyzed
153 with the Living Image v4.7.3 software (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA). The abdomen was
154 defined as region of interest. In all experiments, mice were sacrificed five days after ACT.
155 Organs were harvested and processed for flow cytometry or histology. *In vivo* B cell depletion
156 was achieved by intravenous tail injection of 250 μ g of an anti-CD20 (clone MB20-11,
157 BioXCell, Lebanon, NH, USA, Cat. #BE0356) or a isotype control (IgG2c isotype control,
158 BioXCell, Lebanon, NH, USA, Cat. #BE0366) monoclonal antibody in 100 μ L PBS 14 days
159 prior to ACT, as previously described (64). Blood was collected from the tail vein and stained
160 for flow cytometry to confirm treatment efficacy both before antibody injection and before
161 ACT.

162

163 **Mouse tissue preparation, staining procedures, image acquisition, and analysis**

164 Gut-draining lymph nodes, spleen, and small intestines were dissected. The small intestine was
165 flushed with ice-cold PBS, opened longitudinally, and laid on blotting paper. Organs were fixed
166 in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA, Sigma-Aldrich, Saint-Louis, MO, USA, Cat. #158127)
167 overnight at 4°C. Samples were then washed three times for 10 minutes with ice-cold PBS, and
168 incubated in 30% sucrose in PBS overnight at 4°C. The organs were subsequently embedded
169 in Tissue-Tek (Sakura, Osaka, Japan, cat. #4583) and frozen. 10 μ m thick tissue sections were
170 cut from the different organs and, after 30 minutes of thawing, the sections were fixed with 4%
171 PFA for 5 minutes and then washed three times with room temperature (RT) PBS. The sections
172 were then incubated for 30 minutes in blocking buffer (0.5% bovine serum albumin
173 (AppliChem, Darmstadt, Germany, cat. #A1391), 5% donkey serum (Biowest, Nuaille, France,

174 cat. #S2170), 0.1% Triton X-100 (Merck, Rahway, NJ, USA, cat. #X-100), and 0.01% sodium
175 azide (AppliChem, Darmstadt, Germany, cat. #A1391) in PBS) and then incubated with
176 primary antibodies in blocking buffer overnight at 4°C. The next day sections were washed
177 three times with 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS, and incubated one hour with secondary antibodies.
178 The sections were further washed with 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS and incubated with
179 conjugated streptavidin and incubated one hour at RT. After secondary antibodies the sections
180 were washed with 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS and mounted with Fluoromount-G Mounting
181 Medium, with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, cat. #00-4959-52) and
182 stored at 4°C. Table S4 provides a list of all antibodies used for staining.

183 Fluorescence images were acquired using a Hamamatsu NanoZoomer S60 slide scanner with
184 20x magnification and analyzed with QuPath software v0.5.1 (65). Cell detection was
185 performed with the StarDist extension and the “dsb2018_heavy_augment.pb” pre-trained
186 model (66).

187

188 Supplementary figures:

189

190 **Fig. S1. Cell line phenotypes**

191 (A) TRAC indels of NFAT-Luciferase TCR KO Jurkat cell line as inferred by the ICE CRISPR
192 Analysis Tool (Synthego).

193 (B) Flow cytometry plots showing CD3 and CD4 expression of modified NFAT-Luciferase
194 TCR KO Jurkat cell line compared to its wild-type counterpart.

195 (C) Flow cytometry analysis comparing HLA-ABC and HLA-DQ expression of the generated
196 β 2m KO Raji cell line compared to its wild-type counterpart.

197 (D) CD64 and CD86 expression of K-64.86 cells compared to the wild-type K-562 cell line.

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201 **Fig. S2. NFAT-activity after TCR mRNA electroporation**

202 Bar plots representing the luminescence of glia-α1a (A) and glia-α2 (B) activation normalized
 203 to the OKT3 luminescence signal for all five TCRs (n = 3).

204 Statistics. Data are represented as mean ± SEM. Panels (A) and (B): one-way ANOVA.

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Fig. S3. GFP expression via AAV-mediated knock-in of CD4⁺ T cells

Flow cytometry analysis of TCR and GFP expression in CD4⁺ T cells transduced with an AAV containing the GFP transgene flanked to a BGH terminator instead of the TCR, with or without TRAC editing. This experiment was performed once.

214

215 **Fig. S4. Engineering and validation of gluten-specific human CD8⁺ T cells**

216 (A) Representative flow cytometry showing CD3 expression in purified engineered CD8⁺ T
 217 cells after seven days of culture.

218 (B) Editing efficiencies for CD3- (KO) and CD3⁺ (S2, LS2.8, D2, JR5.1, S16) expression after
 219 seven days of culture.

220 (C) Expansion of UTD and engineered CD8⁺ T cells.

221 (D) Representative flow cytometry of CD25 and CD71 cell expression after a 48-hours co-
 222 culture with β 2m KO Raji cells and 5 μ M of peptide (gated on living CD8⁺CD3⁺ cells).

223 (E) Cumulative data showing the percentage of CD25/CD71 co-expression in CD3⁺CD8⁺ cells.
 224 Each T cell population was compared to the UTD counterpart for each condition.

225 Statistics. Data are represented as mean \pm SEM of five independent experiments using cells
 226 manufactured from five different donors. Panel (E): two-way ANOVA.

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230 **Fig. S5. Gluten-specific response against β2m KO Raji cell line, HLA-DQ2.5⁺ B cells or**
 231 **HLA-DQ2.5⁺ MoDCs**

232 (A) Histograms representing CD80, CD86, and HLA-DQ expression in β2m KO Raji cells, B
 233 cells, and MoDCs.

234 (B) Percentage of CD25 and CD71 co-expression gated in CD4⁺ cells normalized by the
 235 condition pulsed with 5 μM of peptide for each different antigen presenting cells. 0.1 x 10⁶ S2
 236 or D2 eTeffs were plated with 0.05 x 10⁶ β2m KO Raji cells, 0.05 x 10⁶ HLA-DQ2.5⁺ B cells,
 237 or 0.01 x 10⁶ MoDCs with the *glia-α_33mer* at different concentrations (ranging from 5 μM to
 238 5 x 10⁻⁷ μM performing 1:10 dilutions) for 48 hours.

239 Abbreviations. MoDCs, monocyte-derived dendritic cells.

240 Non-linear least squares regression model based on one independent experiment using cells
 241 manufactured from two different donors.

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245 **Fig. S6. TCR co-receptor dependencies.**

246 (A) Bar plots showing the peptide concentration of the EC50 values and 95% CI for both CD4⁺
 247 (white) and CD8⁺ (grey) eTeffs, each expressing one of the five gluten-specific TCRs, in
 248 response to deamidated peptides. CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ eTeff co-cultures were done separately.
 249 CI, confidence interval.

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253 **Fig. S7. S2 and D2 engineered CD4⁺ T cells competitive proliferation assay**

254 (A) Experimental design. Cells were cultured at 1 (S2):1 (D2):0.5 (HLA-DQ2.5⁺ APC) ratio.

255 The glia-α1a and glia-α2 peptides were mixed at different ratios (1:1 ratio corresponds to 1 μM

256 of each peptide). CTV and CFSE dilutions were assessed four days later.

257 (B) Histograms comparing S2 and D2 CD4⁺ eTeff proliferation.

258 One experiment was performed.

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262 **Fig. S8. Murine BMDC differentiation.**

263 (A) Experimental design for the differentiation of murine BMDCs. Cells from the bone marrow
264 of B6-DQ2.5 were harvested and cultured with GM-CSF. On day nine, cells were matured with
265 LPS and either freshly used the day after as antigen-presenting cell or cryopreserved.

266 (B) Representative flow cytometry showing the expression levels of CD11c, HLA-DQ, CD40,
267 and CD86 in matured versus unmatured BMDCs.

268 Abbreviations. BMDC, bone marrow-derived dendritic cell.

269

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287

288 **Fig. S10. Engineered CD4⁺ T cells trafficking and proliferation under different diet**
289 **conditions**

290 Impact of diet on murine S2 CD4⁺ eTeff trafficking and proliferation. Mice were kept under a
291 GFD or a normal gluten-containing chow during the experiment. Oral gavage of PBS or 0.5 mg
292 gli α -33mer was performed one day after ACT. Cumulative data showing the percentage of
293 Thy1.1⁺ CD4⁺ eTeffs (left) and the corresponding CFSE mean fluorescence intensity (MFI,
294 right) in the small intestine, M-LN, and Ma-LN five days after ACT (n = 3-5 per group).

295 Abbreviations. ACT, adoptive cell transfer; GFD, gluten-free diet; LN, lymph node; M,
296 mesenteric; Ma, mandibular. Statistics. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM of one experiment.
297 Statistical method: one-way ANOVA.

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301 **Fig. S11. Bioluminescence of engineered and polyclonal CD4⁺ T cells**

302 (A) Bioluminescence two and four days after infusion of 2×10^6 CD4⁺ T cells into B6-DQ2.5
303 transgenic mice with a standard diet and who received deamidated gliadin gavage one day after
304 adoptive cell transfer.

305 (B) Cumulative data showing total flux signal gated in the abdominal region ($n = 5-9$ per group).
306 Abbreviations. GF, gluten-free; LN, lymph node; M, mesenteric; Ma, mandibular. Statistics.
307 Data are from two independent experiments and presented as mean \pm SEM. Panel (B): two-way
308 ANOVA.

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312 **Fig. S12. Engineered CD4⁺ T cells trafficking and proliferation and gut-homing marker**
 313 **expressions**

314 (A) Flow cytometry histograms comparing GFP expression on polyclonal CD4⁺ T cells from
 315 B6-DQ2.5 and B6-Cas9 mice, and on S2 and D2 CD4⁺ eTeffs from B6-Cas9 mice.

316 (B) Gating strategy on living CD45⁺ cells discriminating between GFP^{neg} (endogenous to B6-
 317 DQ2.5), GFP^{low} cells (non-edited expanded CD4⁺ T cells) and GFP^{high} cells (S2).

318 (C) Representative flow cytometry histograms displaying CTV expression in GFP^{high}, GFP^{low},
 319 and GFP^{neg} cells five days after ACT.

320 (D) Cumulative data representing the CTV mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) for each tissue
 321 comparing the S2-GFP^{high} (red) and non-edited-GFP^{low} (white) CD4⁺ T cells (n = 4, one
 322 experiment).

323 (E) Representative flow cytometry histograms showing CCR9 and α4β7 expression in GFP^{high}
 324 S2 CD4⁺ eTeffs compared to non-edited GFP^{low} CD4⁺ T cells in the duodenum.

325 Abbreviations. ACT, adoptive cell transfer; D, duodenum; I, ileum; J, jejunum.

326 Statistics. Data are presented as mean ± SEM. Panel (D): two-way ANOVA.

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330 **Fig. S13. GFP staining detected only engineered S2-GFP^{high} CD4⁺ T cells**
 331 Representative immunofluorescence images of GFP (green), CD3 (gray), CD4 (red), and DAPI
 332 (blue) expression in mesenteric lymph nodes of B6-DQ2.5 mice adoptively transferred with
 333 PBS, polyclonal CD4⁺ (GFP^{low}), or S2-CD4⁺ (GFP^{high}) T cells expanded from B6-Cas9 mice.
 334 Five days after adoptive transfer. Scale bars, 100 μ m. One experiment.
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Fig. S14. Engineered CD4⁺ T cells intestinal infiltration and proliferation after CD20⁺ B cell depletion

(A) Representative flow cytometry plots and cumulative data showing the percentage of B220⁺CD19⁺ B cells within CD45⁺ cells in peripheral blood at day -14 and -1 before ACT in mice injected with anti-CD20 monoclonal antibody or an isotype control antibody.

(B) Percentage of CD19⁺CD20⁺ cells in the small intestine, mesenteric lymph nodes, and the spleen on day 5 after ACT (day 4).

Abbreviations. ACT, adoptive cell transfer; M-LN, mesenteric lymph nodes; SI, small intestine. Statistics. Data are presented as mean ± SEM from one independent experiment involving 4 (isotype control) and 5 (anti-CD20) mice per group. Each dot represents one mouse. Statistical method: two-way ANOVA.

351

352 **Fig. S15. Engineering and validation of glia- ω 1-reactive murine CD4⁺ T cells**
 353 (A) TCR clone W321 and glia- ω -derived peptide sequences selected from (22).
 354 (B) Map of the AAV gene cassette used to engineer mCherry⁺ W321 CD4⁺ T cells.
 355 (C) Representative CD3, GFP, and mCherry expression in engineered CD4⁺ T cells at day 7
 356 (D) Representative CD25 and CD69 expression in CD4⁺ T cells after overnight co-culture of
 357 0.1×10^6 CD4⁺ T cells with 0.02×10^6 HLA-DQ2.5⁺ BMDCs pulsed with $5 \mu\text{M}$ of the
 358 corresponding peptide. Glia- α refers to glia- α _33mer, and glia- ω to glia- ω _34mer. This
 359 experiment was performed once (n=1).
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Fig. S16. Absolute numbers of eTeffs infiltrating the small intestine.

Absolute numbers of eTeffs were determined by the number of events acquired by flow cytometry and normalized by the length of the small intestine five days after ACT.

Abbreviations. ACT, adoptive cell transfer; SI, small intestine.

Statistics. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM from two independent experiments. Statistical method: two-way ANOVA.